

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Multi-stimuli multi-responsive fully supramolecular orthogonally bound polymer networks

Julien Sautaux, Lucas Montero de Espinosa, Sandor Balog and Christoph Weder*

[†]Adolphe Merkle Institute, University of Fribourg, Chemin des Verdiers 4, CH-1700 Fribourg, Switzerland

Email: christoph.weder@unifr.ch

Table of Contents

General materials and methods	S-2
Materials	S-2
Synthesis of EH-Mebip	S-3
Synthesis of M1	S-3
Synthesis of M2	S-4
Preparation of C1 films	S-4
UV-Vis Titration of EH-Mebip	S-5
UV-Vis Titration of a mixture of EH-Mebip and EH-U-C6-UPy	S-5
UV-Vis Titration of the metal complex	S-5
UV-Vis Titration of M2	S-5
UV-Vis Titration of a mixture of M2 and M1	S-5
Preparation of M1 films	S-5
Preparation of M2-Zn(NTf ₂) ₂ films	S-6
Preparation of (M1) ₁ -(M2·Zn(NTf ₂) ₂) ₁ and (M1) ₂ -(M2·Zn(NTf ₂) ₂) ₁ films	S-6
Shape-memory experiments	S-6
Stimulus-driven healing experiments	S-7
Orthogonal character of the non-covalent interactions	S-8
UV-Vis titration of M2	S-10
UV-Vis titration of a mixture of M2 and M1	S-10
Plot of the absorbance for UV-Vis titration	S-11
FT-IR spectra of C1	S-11
SAXS data analysis	S-12
UV-Vis absorption spectra of a solution of M2·Zn(NTf ₂) ₂ with TMEDA	S-12
SAXS spectra of a film of (M1) ₂ -(M2·Zn(NTf ₂) ₂) exposed to TMEDA	S-13
DSC data of a film of (M1) ₂ -(M2·Zn(NTf ₂) ₂) exposed to TMEDA	S-13
Optical micrograph of damaged films (control experiment)	S-14
Data of stress-strain experiments for healing experiment	S-14
Pictures of films (M1) ₂ -(M2·Zn(NTf ₂) ₂) ₁	S-15
¹ H NMR spectrum of EH-Mebip	S-16
¹³ C NMR spectrum of EH-Mebip	S-16
¹ H NMR spectrum of M1	S-17
¹³ C NMR spectrum of M1	S-17
¹ H NMR spectrum of M2	S-18
¹³ C NMR spectrum of M2	S-18
¹⁹ F NMR spectrum (free amine control)	S-19
MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of M1	S-20
MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of M2	S-20
References	S-21

General materials and methods

Materials. Zinc bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (Strem Chemicals, Inc.), Chelimidamic acid (Intatrade Chemicals GmbH), anhydrous CH₃CN (Acros) and all other solvents and reagents (Sigma Aldrich) were used as received, except spectroscopic grade CHCl₃ (Acros), from which acidic impurities were removed by passage through a plug of dry, activated (Brockman I) basic alumina prior to use. Jeffamine T-5000 polyetheramine with a reported number-average molecular weight (M_n) of 5000 g/mol was generously donated by Huntsman and dried *in vacuo* at 50 °C overnight before use. 1-(6-(3-(2-Ethylhexyl)ureido)hexyl)-3-(6-methyl-4-oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-yl)urea (**EH-U-C6-UPy**) was synthesized as previously reported.¹

Methods. ¹H (400 MHz or 500 MHz), ¹³C (100 MHz), and ¹⁹F (282 MHz) NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVIII HD spectrometer in CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆. ¹H NMR coupling constants are given in Hz. ¹H NMR spectra were referenced against the signal of residual CHCl₃ or DMSO at 7.26 or 2.50 ppm and ¹³C NMR spectra were referenced against the signal of CDCl₃ or DMSO-*d*₆ at 77.0 or 39.52 ppm. A Polymerix software from Sierra Analytics was used for the data analysis of mass spectroscopy experiments and also allowed calculating the weight average molecular weight, M_w . UV-Vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2401 PC spectrophotometer in CHCl₃/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v). FT-IR spectra were measured on a Perkin Elmer Spectrum 65 spectrometer in ATR mode between 800 and 4000 cm⁻¹. Polymer films were prepared by compression molding in a Carver CE Press. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed under N₂ using a Mettler-Toledo STAR system operating at a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C·min⁻¹ in the range of -80 to 250 °C. Dynamic mechanical analyses (DMA) were conducted under N₂ on a TA Instruments DMA Q800 with a heating rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹, a frequency of 1 Hz, and an amplitude of 15 μm in the range of -80 to 300 °C, using tensile clamps and rectangular shaped samples, unless indicated otherwise. Reported mechanical data are averages of 3–10 independent experiments, and all errors are standard deviations. Tensile tests were performed in a TA Instruments DMA Q 800 at 25 °C with a strain rate of 5 %/min using rectangular samples of the following approximate dimensions: 20 mm x 3.5 mm x 0.25 mm and data are reported as averages of 3-5 independent measurements. Young's moduli were calculated from the slope in the linear region between 0 to 0.5 % strain. A creep experiment was performed in a TA Instruments DMA Q 800 at 25 °C with a strain rate of 5 %/min using rectangular samples of the following approximate dimensions: 10 mm x 4.0 mm x 0.25 mm.

Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments were performed on a Rigaku NanoMax camera (Rigaku Innovative Technologies, Auburn Hills, MI). Measurements were performed at room temperature and raw data were processed according to standard procedures. Scattering spectra are presented as a function of the momentum transfer $q = 4\pi\lambda^{-1} \sin(\theta/2)$, where θ is the scattering angle and $\lambda = 0.1524$ nm is the photon wavelength. Optical microscopy images were acquired with an Olympus BX51 microscope with a DP72 digital camera.

Synthesis of EH-Mebip. 4-Hydroxy-2,6-bis(*N*-methylbenzimidazol-2'-yl)pyridine² (HOMEbip, 0.50 g, 1.41 mmol), K₂CO₃ (585 mg, 4.23 mmol), and 1-bromo-2-ethylhexane (0.41 g, 2.12 mmol) were combined in dry DMF (10 mL) and the mixture was stirred under argon atmosphere for 16 h at 80°C. The reaction was cooled to ambient temperature, poured with H₂O (100 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3 x 100 mL). The organic fractions were combined, washed with saturated aqueous NH₄Cl (100 mL), dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting product was filtered through a short pad (1-2 cm) of silica using CHCl₃/MeOH 9:1 as eluent to afford the product as a white solid (525 mg, 80%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ = 7.96 (s, 2H, ArH), 7.88 (d, *J* = 7.0 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.47-7.44 (m, 2H, ArH), 7.42-7.30 (m, 4H, ArH), 4.24 (s, 6H, -NCH₃), 4.14 (d, *J* = 5.5 Hz, 2H, -CH₂OAr-), 1.80 (hept, *J* = 6.1 Hz, 1H, -CH-), 1.61-1.67 (m, 8H, CH₃CH₂CH₂-, -CH₂CH- and CH₃CH₂CH-), 0.94 (dt, 6H, -CH₃), 0.86 (t, 3H, -CH₂CH₃); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 167.0, 151.1, 150.6, 142.6, 137.29, 123.6, 122.9, 120.2, 111.9, 110.0, 71.0, 39.4, 32.6, 30.6, 29.1, 24.0, 23.1, 14.2, 11.2. MS (MALDI-TOF; matrix: DCTB): *m/z* 468.28 (M + H)⁺ (Calculated mass for [C₂₉H₃₃N₅O + H]⁺: 468.28).

Synthesis of M1. An oven-dried round-bottomed flask was charged with Jeffamine T-5000 (9.46 g, 1.89 mmol), 2-(6-isocyanatohexylaminocarbonylamino)-6-methyl-4[1H]pyrimidinone³ (2.50 g, 8.52 mmol) and dry CHCl₃ (75 mL) and the reaction mixture was stirred under argon atmosphere at reflux for 16 h. The viscous white reaction mixture was diluted with 400 mL of CHCl₃ and the solution was filtered. After concentrating the solution to 150 mL, 3-aminopropyl silica gel (5.00 g, 0.6-1.3 mmol/g) was added and the mixture was stirred at 60 °C for 2 h to remove any excess of 2-(6-isocyanatohexylaminocarbonylamino)-6-methyl-4[1H]pyrimidinone. The reaction was cooled to ambient temperature and the silica gel was subsequently removed by filtration and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting material was dried

for 48 h at 50 °C under reduced pressure to give the macromonomer **M1** as a white solid (9.1 g, 86%). ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz) δ = 11.53 (bs, CH₃CNH-), 9.62 (bs, -CH₂NH(C=O)NHC-), 7.30 (bs, -CH₂NH(C=O)NHC-), 5.81-5.78 (m, -CH₂NH(C=O)NHCH-), 5.75 (s, CH=CCH₃), 5.55 (d, CH₂NH(C=O)NHCH-), 3.75-3.17 (bm, -NH(C=O)NHCH-, -OCH₂CH- backbone), 3.12 (q, -CH₂NH(C=O)NHC-), 2.95 (q, -CH₂NH(C=O)NHCH-), 2.10 (s, CH₃C=CH-), 1.53-1.24 (bm, -CH₂CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 1.12-0.81 (m, -CH(CH₃)N(CH₂)₂-, -CH₃ backbone); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO) δ 172.0, 156.6, 154.8, 148.4, 106.8, 75.7, 75.5, 75.4, 75.2, 73.5, 73.2, 73.1, 46.6, 40.2, 39.8, 30.4, 29.5, 26.7, 19.1, 18.5, 17.5. *M*_n = 5600 g/mol by ¹H NMR. *m/z* (MALDI-TOF; matrix: DCTB) *M*_n = 5700 g/mol, *M*_w = 5800 g/mol, PDI = 1.01.

Synthesis of M2. Jeffamine T-5000 (1.00 g, 0.20 mmol) and 2,2'-(4-((6-bromohexyl)oxy)-pyridine-2,6-diyl)bis(1-methyl-1*H*-benzo[d]imidazole) (1.04 g, 2.00 mmol) were suspended in acetonitrile (7.5 mL) and stirred for 15 min at 70 °C. K₂CO₃ (553 mg, 4.00 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred under argon atmosphere at reflux for 96 h. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was dissolved in a mixture of chloroform (70 mL) and water (70 mL). The aqueous phase was extracted with CHCl₃ (3 x 70 mL) and the organic fractions were combined, washed with brine (70 mL) and dried over MgSO₄, filtered, and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The product was dissolved in MeOH (10 mL) and the suspension was filtered. The filtrate containing the polymer was purified by dialysis against MeOH for 3 days to afford macromonomer **M2** orange solid (700 mg, 49%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) δ = 7.92 (s, ArH), 7.85 (d, ArH), 7.48-7.41 (d, ArH), 7.41-7.28 (m, ArH), 4.23 (m, -NCH₃, -CH₂OAr-), 3.83-3.20 (m, -OCH₂CH- backbone), 2.94 (m, -CH(CH₃)N(CH₂)₂-) 2.44 (bt, -CH₂-), 1.86 (t, -CH₂-), 1.52-1.25 (m, -CH₂CH₂CH₂CH₂-), 1.20-1.10 (m, -CHCH₃ backbone), 1.00 (d, -CH(CH₃)N(CH₂)₂-); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 166.7, 151.1, 150.5, 142.5, 137.2, 123.5, 122.8, 120.2, 111.90, 110.0, 75.6, 75.4, 75.3, 75.2, 73.5, 73.0, 73.0, 73.0, 72.9, 71.6, 68.8, 67.3, 65.7, 50.9, 32.6, 29.0, 27.2, 26.0, 17.6, 17.4. *M*_n = 7100 g/mol by UV-Vis titration with Zn(NTf₂)₂. *m/z* (MALDI-TOF; matrix: Dithranol) *M*_n = 7100 g/mol, *M*_w = 7200 g/mol, PDI = 1.01.

Preparation of C1 films. Jeffamine T-5000 (1.00 g, 0.20 mmol) and boron trifluoride ethylamine complex (57 mg, 5 % by weight) were placed in a vial under argon atmosphere and stirred at 50°C until the latter was completely dissolved. 1,6-Hexanediol diacrylate (234 mg, 1.03

mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min at 50 °C. The viscous reaction mixture was cast into a Teflon® Petri dish molded, which was placed in an oven under vacuum at 100 °C for 24 h. The resulting films were removed from oven, cooled to ambient temperature and were washed with DCM (3 x 10 mL) to remove any unreacted 1,6-hexanediol diacrylate and dried for 48 h at 50 °C under reduced pressure to yield 250-300 μm thick elastic films.

UV-Vis Titration of EH-Mebip. A solution of **EH-Mebip** (20.0 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 2 mL) was titrated with 25 μL aliquots of a solution mixture of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (158 μM) and **EH-Mebip** (20.0 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 10 mL). A UV-Vis spectrum was recorded after each aliquot addition. The absorption at 340 nm was plotted against the Zn²⁺:**EH-Mebip** ratio.

UV-Vis Titration of a mixture of EH-Mebip and EH-U-C6-UPy. A solution of **EH-Mebip** (20.0 μM) and **EH-U-C6-UPy** (20.0 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 2 mL) was titrated with 25 μL aliquots of a solution mixture of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (163 μM), **EH-Mebip** (20.0 μM) and **EH-U-C6-UPy** (20.0 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 10 mL). A UV-Vis spectrum was recorded after each aliquot addition. The absorption at 340 nm was plotted against the Zn²⁺:**EH-Mebip** ratio.

UV-Vis Titration of the metal complex. A solution of **EH-Mebip** (20.1 μM) and Zn(NTf₂)₂ (10.0 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 2 mL) was titrated with 25 μL aliquots of a solution mixture of **EH-U-C6-UPy** (172 μM), **EH-Mebip** (20.1 μM) and Zn(NTf₂)₂ (10.0 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 10 mL). A UV-Vis spectrum was recorded after each aliquot addition. The absorption at 340 nm was plotted against the Zn²⁺:**EH-Mebip** ratio.

UV-Vis Titration of M2. A solution of **M2** (6.22 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 2 mL) was titrated with 25 μL aliquots of a solution mixture of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (165 μM) and **M2** (6.22 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 10 mL). A UV-Vis spectrum was recorded after each aliquot addition. The absorption at 340 nm was plotted against the Zn²⁺:**M2** ratio.

UV-Vis Titration of a mixture of M2 and M1. A solution of **M2** (6.22 μM) and **M1** (6.22 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 2 mL) was titrated with 25 μL aliquots of a solution mixture of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (165 μM), **M2** (6.22 μM) and **M1** (6.22 μM) in CH₃Cl/CH₃CN (9/1 v/v, 10 mL). A UV-Vis spectrum was recorded after each aliquot addition. The absorption at 340 nm was plotted against the Zn²⁺:**M2** ratio.

Preparation of M1 films. **M1** (200 mg, 0.03 mmol) was suspended in CH₃Cl (4 mL) and stirred until dissolved. The solution was cast into a Teflon[®] Petri dish with a diameter of 6 cm, which was placed in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 1 day. The samples were removed from the mould and compression-moulded between Teflon[®] sheets in a Carver press at 90 °C and a pressure of 3 tons for 20 min to obtain 200-250 μm thick films.

Preparation of M2-Zn(NTf₂)₂ films. To a stirred solution of **M2** (200 mg, 0.03 mmol) in CHCl₃ (4 mL), a solution of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (53.3 mg, 0.09 mmol) in anhydrous CH₃CN (4 mL) was added and an increase of the solutions viscosity was observed. The solution mixture was stirred for 30 min, cast into a Teflon[®] Petri dish with a diameter of 6 cm, which was placed in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 1 day. The samples were removed from the mould and compression-moulded between Teflon[®] sheets in a Carver press at 100 °C and a pressure of 5 tons for 5 min to obtain 200-250 μm thick films.

Preparation of (M1)₁-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁ and (M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁ films. Representative procedure for (M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁: To a stirred solution of **M1** (237 mg, 0.04 mmol) and **M2** (145 mg, 0.02 mmol) in CHCl₃ (4 mL), a solution of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (39 mg, 0.06 mmol) in anhydrous CH₃CN (4 mL) was added and an increase of the solutions viscosity was observed. The solution mixture was stirred for 30 min, cast into a Teflon[®] Petri dish with a diameter of 6 cm, which was placed in a vacuum oven at 50 °C for 1 day. The samples were removed from the mould and compression-moulded between Teflon[®] sheets in a Carver press at 90 °C and a pressure of 5 tons for 20 min to obtain 200-250 μm thick films. Films of (M1)₁-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁ were made following the same procedure.

Shape-memory experiments. The shape-memory behavior of (M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁ films with approximate dimensions of 10 mm x 5.3 mm x 0.25 mm was studied by DMA in controlled-force mode. Samples were heated to 110 °C, deformed by applying a force of 0.005 N at a rate of 0.005 N·min⁻¹, and cooled to 25 °C at a rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹ to fix the temporary shape. Once the samples reached 25 °C, the temperature was maintained for 10 min before removing the applied force. After waiting for another 5 min to allow for any relaxation, the samples were heated at a rate of 5 °C·min⁻¹ to 110 °C and kept at the final temperature for 10 min to allow recovery of the permanent shape. Three cycles were conducted for each sample and the fixity (%) and recovery (%) ratios were calculated for each cycle according to the Eqs. (1) and (2):⁴

$$\% \text{ Fixity} = \frac{\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_i}{\varepsilon_s - \varepsilon_i} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

$$\% \text{ Recover} = \frac{\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_r}{\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_i} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where, ε_s is the strain after stretching, ε_u is the strain after unloading, ε_r is the recovered strain after heating, and ε_i is the initial strain.

Stimulus-driven healing experiments. Films were damaged by cutting the samples to a depth of ~50–70 % of their thickness with a razor blade attached to a caliper, which allowed for specific depth control. The samples were then exposed to heat (at 150 °C during 5 min) and/or to tetramethylethylenediamine (TMEDA) vapors in a sealed container (25 mL) containing 4 mL of TMDEA (during 3 min) and then dried in a vacuum oven at 25 °C for 12 h . The healing efficiency (%) was calculated according to the Eq. (3):⁵

$$\% \text{ healing efficiency} = \frac{Toughness_{healed}}{Toughness_{original}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Supporting Discussion: Investigation of the orthogonal binding of the non-covalent motifs employed with model compounds

Model compounds 2,2'-(4-((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)pyridine-2,6-diyl)bis(1-methyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole) (**EH-Mebip**, Figure S1a) and 1-(6-(3-(2-ethylhexyl)ureido)hexyl)-3-(6-methyl-4-oxo-1,4-dihydropyrimidin-2-yl)urea¹ (**EH-U-C6-UPy**, Figure S1a) were synthesized to investigate the orthogonality of Zn(Mebip)₂ complexation and UPy dimerization. Previous work from our group focused on assessing the orthogonality of the Mebip-Zn/UPy pair using macromolecular derivatives. Here we sought to use monomeric motifs to exclude polymer chain effects and obtain a more accurate picture of the binding characteristics of both motifs. In a first experiment, either **EH-Mebip** or an equimolar mixture of **EH-Mebip** and **EH-U-C6-UPy** were titrated with aliquots of Zn(NTf₂)₂ (Figure S1b, Figure S1c). The neat **EH-Mebip** shows the absorbance band of the free ligand with an absorption maximum λ_{max} at 314 nm (Figure S1b). Upon addition of Zn(NTf₂)₂, a new band associated with the [Zn(EH-Mebip)₂](NTf₂)₂ complex appears at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 340$ nm and the intensity of the free ligand's absorption centered around 314 nm decreases. This is better visualized in Figure S1d, which shows a plot of the absorbance at 340 nm as a function of the Zn²⁺:**EH-Mebip** ratio. The absorbance increases linearly up to the stoichiometric ratio (1:2 Zn²⁺:**EH-Mebip** ratio), but above this value, the addition of more Zn(NTf₂)₂ does not change the absorbance further (Figure S1d). Using this titration as reference, aliquots of Zn(NTf₂)₂ were added to an equimolar mixture of **EH-Mebip** and **EH-U-C6-UPy**, and the change of the absorbance was monitored by UV-vis spectroscopy (Figure S1c). The initial absorption spectrum displays a superposition of the spectra of the two individual components. As in the first titration, the characteristic band of the newly formed [Zn(EH-Mebip)₂](NTf₂)₂ complex appeared upon addition of Zn(NTf₂)₂. Gratifyingly, a plot of the absorbance at 340 nm as a function of the Zn²⁺:**EH-Mebip** ratio revealed a perfect overlap with the data of the previous titration in which **EH-U-C6-UPy** was absent (Figure S1d). In an additional control experiment, [Zn(EH-Mebip)₂](NTf₂)₂ was titrated with aliquots of **EH-U-C6-UPy** to challenge its stability. As expected, no changes (other than a dilution effect) were observed in the absorbance spectrum upon addition of **EH-U-C6-UPy** (Figure S1e and Figure S1f). Taken together, these results unequivocally confirm that Zn²⁺-Mebip coordination and UPy dimerization are, at least in dilute solution, indeed orthogonal.

Figure S1. (a) Chemical structures of model compounds EH-Mebip and EH-U-C6-UPy, which were used to assess the orthogonality of the binding motifs. (b) UV-Vis absorption spectra recorded upon titrating a solution containing EH-Mebip (20 μM) with Zn(NTf₂)₂ (163 μM). (c) UV-Vis absorption spectra recorded upon titrating a solution containing EH-Mebip and EH-U-C6-UPy (both 20 μM) with Zn(NTf₂)₂ (163 μM) (d) Plot of the absorbance at 340 nm of the spectra shown in (b and c) against the Zn²⁺:EH-Mebip ratio (▲); also shown are the data for the corresponding titration of a solution containing only EH-Mebip (20 μM) (■). (e) UV-Vis absorption spectra recorded upon titrating a solution containing [Zn(EH-Mebip)₂](NTf₂)₂ (20 μM) with EH-U-C6-UPy (172 μM). (f) Plot of the absorbance at 340 nm of the spectra shown in (e) against the EH-U-C6-UPy:MSC (metallo-supramolecular complex) ratio. A 9/1 v/v CHCl₃/CH₃CN mixture was used as solvent throughout.

Figure S2. UV-Vis spectra recorded for the titration of a solution of **M2** with $\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2$. Data were acquired upon adding 25 μL aliquots of a $\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2$ solution in a 9:1 v/v $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ mixture (165 μM) to a solution of **M2** (6.22 μM) in the same solvent mixture.

Figure S3. UV-Vis spectra recorded for the titration of a solution containing a mixture of **M2** and **M1** with $\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2$. Data were acquired upon adding 25 μL aliquots of a $\text{Zn}(\text{NTf}_2)_2$ solution in a 9:1 v/v $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ mixture (165 μM) to a solution of a mixture of **M2** and **M1** (6.22 μM for each) in the same solvent mixture.

Figure S4. Plot of the absorbance at 340 nm of the spectrum shown in Figure S2 (■) and Figure S3(▲) as a function of the Zn²⁺: M2 ratio showing complexation at 3:1 ratio even in presence of M1.

Figure S5. (a) Fourier-Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectra of the starting reaction mixture of C1 (black), after 1 h (green) and after 24 h (orange). The strong signals associated to the double bond completely disappear after 24 h confirming the complete consumption of the diacrylate moieties in the cross-linking reaction. (b) FT-IR spectra of C1 (orange) and C1 that was heated at 200 °C for 10 min under N₂ atmosphere (black). The signals associated to the double bond reappear after 24 h heating at 200 °C confirming the decomposition of C1 via retro aza-Michael addition.

Table S1. Results of SAXS data analysis. Lamellar period is calculated as $2\pi/q$.

	q_1 (nm^{-1})	q_2 (nm^{-1})	Characteristic length (nm)
C1	0.894	-	7.03
M1	0.797	1.611	7.88 (lamellar)
M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂	0.744	1.489	8.45 (lamellar)
(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁	0.771	1.548	8.15 (lamellar)
(M1)₁-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁	0.744	1.492	8.45 (lamellar)

Figure S6. Evolution of the UV-Vis absorption spectra of a solution of **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** (6.6 μM) in 9/1 v/v $\text{CHCl}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{CN}$ upon addition of TMEDA. The figure shows the spectrum of the original solution (red) and the solutions after addition of increasing equivalents of TMEDA.

Figure S7. SAXS spectra of a film of $(\mathbf{M1})_2-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ (solid line) and of a film of $(\mathbf{M1})_2-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ exposed to TMEDA vapors for 3 min (dotted line). (Samples were measured in a quartz glass capillary)

Figure S8. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) traces (1st heating, heating rate $20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$; please note that the heating rate is higher than in the DSC traces of Figure 3a to better visualize the thermal transitions) of films of supramolecular networks $(\mathbf{M1})_2-(\mathbf{M2}\cdot\mathbf{Zn}(\mathbf{NTf}_2)_2)_1$ before (solid line) and after (dotted line) exposure to TMEDA vapors for 3 min.

Figure S9. Optical micrograph showing the surface of previously damaged films of **M1** and **M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂** before and after exposure to TMEDA vapors for 3 min. (left) or after heating in the oven at 150 °C for 5 min. (right). (Scale bar = 200 μm.)

Table S2. Data of stress-strain experiments. Toughness values were calculated from the integral of the area below the stress-strain curves. Data represent averages from three to five samples per film measured.

(M1)₂-(M2·Zn(NTf₂)₂)₁	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Strain at break (%)	Toughness (kJ m ⁻³)
Original	17.5 ± 1.4	1.1 ± 0.1	15.3 ± 3.4	124 ± 17
Damaged	18.2 ± 0.7	0.84 ± 0.07	7.1 ± 0.6	36.2 ± 5.8
TMEDA	23.3 ± 3.2	1.1 ± 0.1	11.0 ± 0.2	80.3 ± 4.6
150°C	15.9 ± 2.2	0.89 ± 0.06	11.5 ± 1.4	67.1 ± 8.8
150°C & TMEDA	16.8 ± 2.0	1.2 ± 0.2	15.3 ± 2.7	125 ± 32

Figure S10. Pictures of films of $(M1)_2-(M2 \cdot Zn(NTf_2)_2)_1$. (a) Picture showing a freshly prepared film (top) and a film stored during 3 months under ambient condition (bottom). (b) Pictures showing a film before (left) and after exposure to TMEDA vapors for 3 min (right). (c) Pictures showing a film before (left) and after heating on a hot stage at $110^\circ C$ (right).

Figure S11. Creep experiment of a film of $(M1)_2-(M2 \cdot Zn(NTf_2)_2)_1$ showing the evolution over time of stress under a constant strain at room temperature.

Figure S12. ¹H NMR spectrum of 2,2'-(4-((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)pyridine-2,6-diyl)bis(1-methyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole) (EH-Mebip).

Figure S13. ¹³C NMR spectrum of 2,2'-(4-((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)pyridine-2,6-diyl)bis(1-methyl-1*H*-benzo[*d*]imidazole) (EH-Mebip).

Figure S14. ^1H NMR spectrum of **M1**.

Figure S15. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **M1**.

Figure S16. ^1H NMR spectrum of **M2**.

Figure S17. ^{13}C NMR spectrum of **M2**.

Figure S18. ^{19}F NMR spectrum of (a) 3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)benzaldehyde (BTFBA), (b) Jeffamine T-5000 with BTFBA, (c) **M1** with BTFBA, and **M2** with BTFBA. The peak at -63.05 ppm corresponds to the BTFBA and the peak at -62.97 ppm corresponds to the BTFBA reacted with the primary amine. Complete end-capping of the primary amine end-groups was confirmed by the absence of the signal at -62.97 ppm in the cases of **M1** (c) and **M2** (d).⁶

Figure S19. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of **M1**.

Figure S20. MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of **M2**.

References

- (1) Balkenende, D. W. R.; Monnier, C. A.; Fiore, G. L.; Weder, C. Optically responsive supramolecular polymer glasses. *Nature Communications* **2016**, *7*, 10995.
- (2) Rowan, S. J.; Beck, J. B. Metal-ligand induced supramolecular polymerization: A route to responsive materials. *Faraday Discuss.* **2005**, *128*, 43-53.
- (3) Sijbesma, R. P.; Beijer, F. H.; Brunsveld, L.; Folmer, B. J. B.; Hirschberg, J. H. K. K.; Lange, R. F. M.; Lowe, J. K. L.; Meijer, E. W. Reversible Polymers Formed from Self-Complementary Monomers Using Quadruple Hydrogen Bonding. *Science* **1997**, *278*, 1601-1604.
- (4) Lendlein, A.; Kelch, S. Shape-Memory Polymers. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2002**, *41*, 2034-2057.
- (5) Burnworth, M.; Tang, L.; Kumpfer, J. R.; Duncan, A. J.; Beyer, F. L.; Fiore, G. L.; Rowan, S. J.; Weder, C. Optically healable supramolecular polymers. *Nature* **2011**, *472*, 334-337.
- (6) Ji, S.; Hoye, T. R.; Macosko, C. W. Primary Amine ($-NH_2$) Quantification in Polymers: Functionality by ^{19}F NMR Spectroscopy. *Macromolecules* **2005**, *38*, 4679-4686.